

Impact of Grounding System Modeling on Overvoltage Waveforms for Direct Lightning Strikes at Wind Turbines

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Abstract—Wind farms represent a fundamental component of the worldwide transition to renewable energy. However, wind turbines are exposed to lightning strikes due to their tall structures. In this context, adequate modeling of wind turbines is essential to determine the generated overvoltages during a lightning strike. One of the key parts of the wind turbine is the grounding system, where lightning current must be dissipated into the soil, ensuring that a safe earth potential is maintained. This paper investigates distinct grounding system models and their impact on the generated overvoltages in the nacelle and tower base when a wind turbine is struck by lightning. The analysis is performed considering a realistic wind turbine grounding system (WTGS) using the full-wave electromagnetic FEKO/Altair Engineering[®] to calculate its harmonic impedance for the frequency range 100 Hz to 10 MHz. Based on this impedance, the low-frequency resistance R_{LF} and the impulse impedance Z_p are computed. Soils represented by four distinct values of low-frequency resistivity ρ_0 are assumed: 500, 1,000, 2,500 and 5,000 $\Omega \cdot m$. The software ATP-EMTP[®] is used for the circuit model of the wind turbine and numerical simulations. Results demonstrated that significant differences can be obtained for the on the GPR and overvoltage waveforms at the nacelle and tower base, where the use of R_{LF} tends to underestimate the transient responses whilst Z_p is a more adequate and concise representation of the grounding system.

Index Terms—electromagnetic transients, lightning, wind turbines, grounding system

I. INTRODUCTION

Wind power has emerged as a crucial renewable energy source, playing a significant role in the recent global transition from traditional fossil fuels to more sustainable energy matrices. As a result of this growth, wind turbines (WTs) are being designed with taller structures to increase the electrical power extracted from the wind and are installed in locations with consistent and strong wind speeds. Typically, these locations are characterized by unobstructed and elevated terrains, such as hilltops or coastal areas, where wind flow is less turbulent and more predictable. The combination of these factors makes wind turbines excellent lightning initiators, posing a significant engineering challenge. When lightning strikes a wind turbine, the overvoltages can harm the electrical components, such as the generator and transformer in the nacelle, and the ground potential rise (GPR) at the tower base can endanger the safety of individuals working nearby [1], [2]. In this context, it is essential to accurately model each WT component, such as

the grounding system (GS), blades, and tower for the transient analysis during a lightning strike. This accurate representation is crucial to overcoming these problems. Sophisticated full-wave electromagnetic software, such as CDEGS[®] [3], and XGSLAB[®] [4], can be used for a precise analysis of the transient responses, where they utilize numerical methods to solve Maxwell's equation, especially at high frequencies, where the mutual coupling between elements is significant, affecting the precision of the results. Some of the most used methods are the Method of Moments (MoM), the Finite Element Method (FEM), and the Partial Element Equivalent Circuit (PEEC). However, these simulations consume considerable computational time depending on the size of the structure, discretization mesh, and boundaries of the studied system. Alternatively, a simpler approach can be adopted to represent some parts of WT (blades and tower) by distributed circuits, employing the Transmission Line Model (TLM). This model which consists of dividing the WT into a certain number of distinct segments and equivalent circuits consisting of distributed resistance, capacitance, and inductance is simulated in the EMTP-type programs, such as ATP-EMTP[®] [5], PSCAD[®] [6].

Concerning the wind turbine grounding system (WTGS) can be represented by a distinct approaches based on: (a) low-frequency (or static) resistance R_{LF} , given by ratio of the instantaneous values of developed GPR and the injected current at calculated at the wave tail [7]; (b) Equivalent electric circuit model obtained by the approximation of the harmonic grounding impedance $Z_h(j\omega)$ into a rational function using the Vector Fitting technique [8]–[10]. (c) Impulse impedance Z_p , given by the ratio between the maximum GPR over maximum current, where a simple resistance equivalent to Z_p is added at the base of the wind turbine [2].

Additionally, full-wave electromagnetic modeling has been employed to model wind farms under transient state generated for the lightning strikes [11], [12]. Azevedo *et al.* investigated the effect of different soil modeling proposed in the literature concerning physical factors such as water content, porosity and frequency effect in [11]. In this paper, the wind turbine grounding system (WTGS) is represented by the impulse impedance Z_p for each soil model analyzed. Results showed

that transient overvoltages generated by lightning strikes on wind turbines are considerably influenced by these physical factors. The influence of the grounding system on induced voltages on a medium-voltage transmission line for an indirect lightning strike has been investigated for the in [13]. To the best of the author's knowledge, an investigation into overvoltages generated on wind turbines for distinct grounding systems has not been examined in the existing literature. Therefore, this paper aims to evaluate this impact on transient responses, addressing distinct grounding models while taking into account soil resistivity and lightning current.

This work investigates the transient responses generated for a WT hit by a direct lightning strike, using two distinct models to represent the wind turbine grounding system. One model is using the low-frequency resistance and the other is using the impulse impedance. Additionally, this study incorporates a realistic soil model with frequency-dependent electrical parameters. The voltages at the nacelle and tower base (GPR) of the WT are calculated for distinct values of soil resistivity and two lightning currents. The transient responses differ significantly between the models when WT are subjected to lightning strikes. These differences can affect the design of electrical insulation of equipment and an adequate design of the grounding system must provide a safe earth potential rise to personnel during a lightning strike. The main contribution of this work is the comparison between transient responses calculated by two commonly grounding system models used in literature with a lumped circuit representing the wind turbine incorporate in the ATP-EMTP®.

II. WIND TURBINE MODELING-LUMPED APPROACH

A generic wind turbine located on a lossy soil and the modeling of each part is illustrated in Fig. 1.

A. Blade Modeling

The blade is represented by a thin wire approach, using a transmission line model whose surge impedance Z_b , expressed by [2]

$$Z_b = 60 \left[\ln \left(4 \frac{h_b}{r_b} \right) - 1 \right], \quad (1)$$

where h_b (m) is the height from the ground, and r_b (m) is the blade radius, approximated as a thin rod. The propagation velocity v_b is assumed to be $0.65c$, where c is the speed of light. This reduced value is due to the Skin effect on the rotor blade and the capacitive effect of the blade's structure [14].

B. Tower Modeling

The tower is modeled as cascaded sequence of cylinders representing each section of the structure. Each section is modeled as lossless lines as depicted in Fig. 1-(b) where the tower is divided into four sections (S_i). Each lossless line is represented by a conductor of length ℓ_i associated with a surge impedance Z_i and a propagation velocity v_t , as detailed in Fig. 1-(c). The surge impedance of each cylinder Z_i is given by [2]

$$Z_i = 60 \left[\ln \left(2\sqrt{2} \frac{h_i}{r_i} \right) - 1 \right], \quad (2)$$

where h_i (m) is the height from ground and r_i (m) is the radius of the base. The propagation velocity v_t is assumed to be $0.85c$, according to [15].

C. Tower Footing Grounding System Modeling

Ground can be modeled by its electrical conductivity σ , permittivity ε , and magnetic permeability μ , respectively. Additionally, it is known in the literature that the soil is a dielectric medium and its electrical parameters are dependent on the frequency effect due to the several processes of polarization in the ground particles [16]–[18]. In order evaluate the impact of the frequency effect on the soil parameters, the Alipio-Visacro's model are assumed and it is recommended by CIGRE [18]. The frequency-dependent (FD) resistivity and relative permittivity are:

$$\rho(f) = \rho_0 \{1 + 4.7 \times 10^{-6} f^{0.54} \rho_0^{0.73}\}^{-1} \quad (3)$$

$$\varepsilon_r(f) = 12 + 9.5 \times 10^4 \rho_0^{-0.27} f^{-0.46} \quad (4)$$

where ρ_0 , in $\Omega \cdot m$, is the low-frequency resistivity measured at 100 Hz and f , in Hz, is the frequency. The wind turbine grounding system (WTGS) of the wind turbine is shown in Fig. 1-(d).

The harmonic grounding impedance (HGI) $Z_h(j\omega)$ of a vertical rod or horizontal electrode buried in a lossy ground is calculated using the full-wave electromagnetic software FEKO using Method of Moments (MoM) [19]. In this software, the electrode grounding system is buried into a dielectric medium (soil) characterized by its soil electrical parameters ρ , ε_r and μ_0 . Once the harmonic impedance is calculated, the frequency-dependent $Z_h(j\omega)$ can be fitted as pole-residue model obtained by the Vector Fitting technique [8], where a lumped equivalent circuit can be associated depending on the nature of the pole (real or complex) [9]. Finally, this equivalent circuit can be incorporated in any time-domain electromagnetic transient simulations, such as ATP-EMTP or PSCAD [5], [6].

The transient GPR $v(t)$ developed for a certain injected current $i(t)$, from a remote point, is given as follows the GPR is given expressed by

$$GPR = \mathcal{F}^{-1} \{I(j\omega) \times Z_g\}, \quad (5)$$

where the \mathcal{F}^{-1} denotes the inverse Fourier Transform, and $I(j\omega)$ is Fourier transform of the injected current and Z_g is the impedance adopted for each grounding system modeling (R_{LF} , Z_P or $Z_h(j\omega)$) respectively. Additionally, the GPR can be computed by a recursive convolution method as proposed by [20]. The wind turbine grounding system (WTGS) impedance can be also represented by the impulse impedance, expressed by [21]

$$Z_p = \frac{\max[GPR]}{\max[i(t)]} = \frac{V_p}{I_p}, \quad (6)$$

where V_p and I_p are the peak values of the GPR developed and injected lightning current, respectively. The advantage

Fig. 1: (a) Wind turbine (WT) hit by a direct lightning strike; (b) Wind tower modeled by cylindrical sections; (c) Equivalent circuit model of WT; (d) wind turbine grounding system (WTGS) of the WT designed in FEKO [upper and side views]; (e) Implemented circuit model in ATP-EMTP to study the impact of grounding system in the wind turbine subjected to lightning strikes. (Not to scale)

TABLE I: Geometrical and electrical parameters of the tower

i - Section (S)	h_i (m)	d_i (m)	ℓ_i (m)	Z_i (Ω)	v_t (m/s)
1	88,17	2,33	28,50	262	0.85c
2	59,50	3,20	28,445	219	0.85c
3	31,055	3,60	16,655	173	0.85c
4	15,570	4,04	15,57	125	0.85c

TABLE II: Values of $Z_{L,F}$ (Ω) and Z_p (Ω) for WTGS

ρ_0 ($\Omega \cdot m$)	First Return Stroke		Subsequent Return Stroke	
	$Z_{L,F}$	Z_p	$Z_{L,F}$	Z_p
500	2.20	5.68	2.20	18.99
1,000	4.50	6.99	4.50	22.04
2,500	11.10	9.25	11.10	26.02
5,000	21.90	14.60	21.90	28.75

TABLE III: Parameters of the lightning currents [22]

Current type	k	I_0 (kA)	n	τ_1 (μs)	τ_2 (μs)
First Return Stroke (FRS) ($T_{10} = 5.20\mu s, T_{30} = 3.0\mu s$)	1	6	2	3	76
	2	5	3	3.5	10
	3	5	5	4.8	30
	4	8	9	6	26
	5	16.5	30	7	200
	6	17	2	70	200
	7	12	14	12	26
Subsequent Return Stroke (SRS) ($T_{10} = 0.50\mu s, T_{30} = 0.3\mu s$)	1	10.7	2	0.25	2.5
	2	6.5	2	2	230

of Z_p is its concise representation as a pure resistance for a grounding system subjected to a lightning current, which produces the same peak value of the GPR. Additionally, the impulse impedance Z_p of any grounding arrangement can be measured in the field with proper equipment, and the peak value of the GPR can be computed directly without using electromagnetic software to model the grounding system [7].

D. Lightning current modeling

The lightning strikes are represented as a current source and a channel resistance R_{ch} injected at the tip of the blade, as illustrated in Fig. 1-(c). In this work, lightning currents representative of the first (FRS) and subsequent return strokes (SRS) are considered. Their waveshapes are mathematically represented by Heidler's functions, expressed as

$$i(t) = \sum_{k=1}^m \frac{I_{0k}}{\eta_k} \frac{e^{-t/\tau_{2k}} (t/\tau_{1k})^{n_k}}{1 + (t/\tau_{1k})^{n_k}}; \eta_k = e^{-\left(\frac{\tau_{1k}}{\tau_{2k}}\right) \left(n_k \frac{\tau_{2k}}{\tau_{1k}}\right)^{1/n_k}}, \quad (7)$$

where I_{0k} is the current amplitude, τ_{1k} is the front-time constant, τ_{2k} is the decay-time constant, n_k is a steepness factor, and η_k is a peak correction factor. The lightning parameters are given in Table III [22]. The T_{10} , T_{30} refer to the time difference between an increase from 10% to 90% and 30% to 90% before the first peak, respectively.

III. NUMERICAL RESULTS

The wind turbine circuit is represented in software ATP-EMTP [5], as illustrated in Fig. 1-(e). As seen in this figure, the lightning current is modeled using the component MODEL associated with a current source and a channel resistance R_{ch} of $400\ \Omega$. The lightning parameters of the first return stroke (frs) and subsequent return stroke (srs) are incorporated via programming code in the MODEL. The lightning current waveforms of the first return stroke (frs) and subsequent return stroke (srs) are illustrated in Fig. 2. The lightning current parameters are shown in Table III. The blades are modeled by a lossless transmission line with surge impedance of Z_b and propagation velocity v_b . The blade has a length ℓ_b of $47.5\ m$ and radius r_b of $5\ mm$. Considering that the WT height h_t is $88\ m$, the height from the soil h_b is $135.70m$. Using (1), the Z_b is equal to $610\ \Omega$, approximately. The tower structure is modeled by four lossless transmission lines with surge impedance of

Fig. 2: Waveforms of the lightning currents representative of FRS and SRS: (a) time-domain and (b) frequency-domain magnitude of the Fourier Transform.

Fig. 3: Harmonic impedance of the Wind Turbine Grounding System for distinct soil resistivities: (a) Magnitude; (b) Phase.

Z_i and propagation velocity v_t . The tower parameters were estimated using (2), and the values are organized in Table I. The wind turbine grounding system of the wind turbine is represented by a GROUP, where the impedance can be the low-frequency resistance R_{LF} or the impulse impedance Z_p , depending on the soil resistivity and lightning current. The numerical results are divided into the following sections:

A. Harmonic grounding impedance of the wind turbines

The HGI of the wind turbine considering the distinct low-frequency soil resistivity is illustrated in Fig. 3. According to this figure, the impedance at low frequencies (between 100 Hz and few tens kHz), present almost constant value. This region is the so-called low-frequency resistance R_{LF} , which is proportional to the low-frequency soil resistivity ρ_0 . The values of R_{LF} for each soil are indicated in the Fig. 3-(a). Above a certain frequency, between 10 kHz and 100 kHz, the reactive part of the harmonic impedance predominates, presenting either inductive or capacitive behavior, depending on the frequency range and low-frequency soil resistivity ρ_0 , as confirmed by the phase in Fig. 3-(b). The impact of the low frequency soil resistivity is investigated in the next section.

B. Ground Potential Rise

To investigate the influence of low-frequency resistivity, the transient GPR is calculated for lightning currents rep-

resentative of the first and subsequent return strokes, which are injected at the feed point (middle of the arrangement), assuming a reference in the remote ground. For this objective, the GPR in (5) is calculated with the recursive method in presented in [20], assuming a time step Δt of 0.1 ns. The computed GPR waveforms, assuming only the harmonic grounding impedance $Z_h(j\omega)$, for the first and subsequent return strokes are illustrated in Fig. 4 (in blue lines). According to this figure, the GPR waveforms is expressively influenced by the low-frequency resistivity ρ_0 , and lightning current waveforms. Furthermore, the GPR are also calculated assuming the low-frequency resistance R_{LF} , using the values indicated in the Fig. 3 for each soil resistivity. These GPR waveforms are illustrated in Fig. 4 (in red lines). As can be seen from this figure, the transient GPR calculated with R_{LF} produces a proportional waveform of its respective lightning current, which increases with the increase of the low-frequency resistivity ρ_0 . However, these waveforms have lower peak values for soils with low resistivity [see Fig. 4-(a), (b),(c), (d), (f) and (h)] but the peak can be higher than those calculated for $Z_h(j\omega)$ considering soils with high resistivity value, as seen in Fig. 4-(e) and (g).

Based on the GPR waveform, the impulse impedance can be calculated using (6) for each low-frequency resistivity and lightning current. The computed values of Z_p are shown in Table II. According to this table, the impulse impedance

Fig. 4: GPR developed for the first return stroke (FRS)[on the left] and subsequent return stroke [on the right] assuming the three distinct GS models ($Z(j\omega)$, R_{LF} and Z_p) and soil with ρ_0 of: (a)-(b) 500 $\Omega \cdot m$; (c)-(d) 1,000 $\Omega \cdot m$; (e)-(f) 2,500 $\Omega \cdot m$; (g)-(h) 5,000 $\Omega \cdot m$.

Z_p varies significantly with the peak of the developed GPR and lightning current waveform. Concerning the impulse impedance computed for the lightning current of first return stroke, depending on the low frequency soil resistivity, the impulse impedance Z_p can be higher than R_{LF} , for soils of low

resistivity value or lower than R_{LF} , for soils of high resistivity value. Regarding the lightning current of subsequent return stroke, the Z_p is higher than R_{LF} , due to the wider frequency content of this current, which is related to its shorter front time, compared with the first return stroke, as illustrated in

Fig. 5: Overvoltage waveforms for obtained for distinct GS models at point A (nacelle) developed by FPI [on the left] and SNI [on the right] assuming soil with ρ_0 of: (a)-(b) 500 Ω .m; (c)-(d) 1,000 Ω .m; (e)-(f) 2,500 Ω .m; (g)-(h) 5,000 Ω .m.

Fig. 2-(b).

The GPR developed for the impulse impedance Z_p is illustrated in Fig. 4 (in black lines). Furthermore, the GPR developed for the Z_p is also proportional to its injected lightning current, having exactly the same peak values. How-

ever, the GPR waveforms vary considerably compared to those generated with $Z_h(j\omega)$ because the harmonic grounding impedance takes into account the reactive behavior (either capacitive or inductive) that occurs at higher frequencies for the grounding system subjected to the fast-front phenomena.

Fig. 6: Overvoltage waveforms for obtained for distinct GS models at point B (tower base) developed by FPI [on the left] and SNI [on the right] assuming soil with ρ_0 of: (a)-(b) 500 $\Omega.m$; (c)-(d) 1,000 $\Omega.m$; (e)-(f) 2,500 $\Omega.m$; (g)-(h) 5,000 $\Omega.m$;

C. Overvoltages generated at nacelle and tower base

The overvoltages generated at the nacelle (Point A) and tower base (Point B) are computed using the circuit shown in Fig. 1-(e) in software ATP-EMTP [5]. The time step of 1 ns is adopted for time-domain simulations. The transient voltages

at the nacelle (Point A) and tower base (point B) for the distinct values of low-frequency soil resistivity are plotted in Figs. 5 and 6, respectively. According to these figures, general observations can be made where the influence of the grounding model of the wind turbine on the overvoltage waveforms is

very important which the differences tends to increase with the low-frequency soil resistivity ρ_0 .

According to Fig. 5, the overvoltages calculated with Z_p and R_{LF} present practically similar values during the first instants of the transient, as seen from 0 to 7.5 μs for the first return stroke (on the left side) and from 0 to 2 μs for the subsequent return stroke, on the right side. Furthermore, the peak values increase with the low-frequency soil resistivity ρ_0 . However, the overvoltages at the wavetail is very sensitive to the grounding model utilized in the wind turbine and the lightning current, where soils with low resistivity show lower values during the steady state. These low values occur due to the Z_p is lower than R_{LF} . However, as the low-frequency soil resistivity ρ_0 increases, the behavior changes especially for soil of high resistivity values. Finally, concerning the lightning current waveforms, the subsequent return stroke presents higher propagation velocity due to its shorter front time, presenting wider frequency range and higher energy at high frequencies, compared with the first return stroke as depicted in Fig. 2. However, for the FRS, the lower front-time results in an increasing δ , being small for grounds with low- and moderate-resistive values (500 and 1,000 $\Omega\cdot\text{m}$) but very elevated for high-resistive soils (2,500 and 5,000 $\Omega\cdot\text{m}$).

According to Fig. 6, the overvoltages at the tower base (point B) have pronounced differences in their waveform depending on the grounding model and lightning current. These differences increases for the increasing low-frequency resistivity ρ_0 , and those assessed with subsequent return stroke have presented the highest difference, as seen in Fig. 6, on the right side. Additionally, multiple reflections on the overvoltage at the tower base are generated by the subsequent return stroke until the steady state is reached. These reflections are related to due to the faster propagation velocity of the surge current waves of subsequent stroke compared with those associated with the first return stroke.

According to these simulation results, different transient overvoltages are obtained when distinct models are employed to represent the wind turbine grounding system. Personnel working near the wind turbine can be exposed to dangerous earth potential rises during transient states. Therefore, a well-designed grounding system with low impedance is fundamental to providing a safe potential for people near these structures. Additionally, most sensitive equipment, such as generators, transformers, and control and power electronic systems, is located in the nacelle compartment. The transient overvoltages may cause malfunctions or damage to these components when wind turbines are exposed to lightning.

IV. CONCLUSIONS

This paper investigates the impact of grounding system modeling on the transient responses of a wind turbine subjected to lightning strikes, including both first and subsequent return strokes. The results demonstrate a significant difference in the transient responses calculated using R_{LF} and Z_p . This difference is dependent on the value of the low-frequency soil resistivity, the lightning current, and the

position along the turbine tower where the overvoltages are calculated. The low-frequency resistance R_{LF} increases with increasing low-frequency soil resistivity. On the other hand, the impulse impedance Z_p is dependent on the harmonic impedance of the wind turbine grounding system, where the reactive part (inductive or capacitive behavior) predominates at higher frequencies. Consequently, Z_p may assume values either higher or lower than R_{LF} for the same soil. Results indicate that Z_p increases with the increase in low-frequency soil resistivity. There is little difference in the overvoltages generated at the nacelle during the initial moments of the transient state for the lightning currents of both the first and subsequent return strokes. However, remarkable differences are observed in the steady-state response, which is governed by the grounding system model. Additionally, the grounding system model significantly affects the overvoltages generated at the tower base, especially when the lightning current from a subsequent return stroke is injected into the wind turbine. These differences are caused by the broader frequency range of this type of lightning current, which has a shorter front time (higher derivative) than the first return stroke. Furthermore, soil resistivity decreases considerably at higher frequencies, which contributes to the differences between the grounding system model becoming smaller as the low-frequency soil resistivity increases. It was found that the low-frequency resistance R_{LF} is not an adequate representation of the wind turbine grounding system under fast-front transients, as it leads to an underestimation of the generated transient responses. Therefore, a grounding system model represented by a pure resistance is not valid and must be replaced by the impulse impedance Z_p , which includes the frequency-dependent effects and the lightning current waveform.

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